

EVALUATION OF THE ASSOCIATION OF MATERNAL DIET WITH STUNTING IN AN URBAN POPULATION OF FAISALABAD, PAKISTAN

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Abstract

Background: Stunting is a form of impaired growth and development that affects around 12 million children in Pakistan, primarily due to poor fetal and maternal nutrition. As stunting is largely irreversible, antenatal care and maternal diet are critical intervention points. Reducing stunting is a key Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) to be achieved by 2030.

Materials and Methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted in Faisalabad city to assess the association between maternal diet and stunting. A total of 401 women with children under 36 months were randomly selected. Data were collected through a structured survey on maternal demographics, anthropometric measurements, and dietary practices. Relevant statistical techniques were applied to analyze relationships between maternal diet and child height-for-age Z-scores.

Results: Maternal nutrition was strongly associated with childhood stunting. Consumption of chapati/bread, cooked cereals, legumes, beef, beans, eggs, cheese, tomatoes, mangoes, potatoes, avocados, and tea showed significant correlations with height-for-age Z-scores. Diet quality during pregnancy was directly linked to children's linear growth. Poor maternal nutrition increased the risk of growth failure, while diverse food intake contributed to better child nutritional outcomes. Findings confirm that children's stunting is interrelated with maternal dietary patterns during pregnancy, and the consequences may be irreversible.

Conclusion: Maternal diet plays a decisive role in preventing stunting. Promoting balanced nutrition during pregnancy is essential for safeguarding child growth and achieving national SDG targets.

INTRODUCTION

Stunting is most common in Asia and Africa. Stunting is commonly related to increased morbidity and mortality, decreased neurocognitive working, reduced learning ability and productivity, and poor health outcomes (Suryawan et al., 2022). From conception to the end of the second year of life, optimal nutrition has a significant role in long-

term health. To achieve better long-term health first 1000 days are crucial (Thurow, 2016). According to UNICEF/WHO stunted population worldwide is 151 million children (Jawaldeh et al., 2020). Childhood stunting is associated with a higher risk of chronic diseases in later life (Prendergast & Humphrey, 2014). A chronically inadequate diet may explain sub-

optimal linear growth. Food-insecure households produce the most stunted individuals (Misselhorn & Hendriks, 2017). In lower and middle-income countries, the role of stunting and childhood growth restriction has drawn particular attention. Progress indicators were included in the Millennium Development Goals to address children's undernutrition (Oruamabo, 2015). In case of failure to address, this issue will compromise the development potential of both individuals and society (Stevens *et al.*, 2012). Upgrading mother's health was mandatory for reducing child stunting in the sub-Saharan country (Buisman *et al.*, 2019). Without a change in environment, stunting is generally assumed to be irreversible (Dhingra & Pingali, 2021) as stunted children don't attain maximum genetic capacity at a later stage, so they impose a heavy burden on human resources, i.e., low economic productivity. It is estimated that as adults, stunted children earn 20% less (McGovern *et al.*, 2017). Due to poor early childhood growth and development, economic losses in Pakistan are around US \$7.6 billion annually (Wieser *et al.*, 2017). From 2000 to 2017, there was a reduction in the stunting rate in Asia from 38% to 23%. Still, it is a higher rate (Dhingra & Pingali, 2021). The stunting rate in Punjab was 36% in 2011, in 2014 it decreased to 33.5%. Punjab subscribes to more than 52% of the national income, and almost 56% of the population resides in Punjab. Females were more likely to have a stunting rate than males (Nuruddin & Hadden, 2015). A study using MICS 2011 data revealed that females had a 26% lower rate of childhood stunting in Punjab (Khalid & Martin, 2017). In South Asia, Pakistan's rate of exclusive breastfeeding is meager and regarded as the leading cause of child stunting (Benedict *et al.*, 2018). Adequate nutrition is necessary for optimum growth of health, strengthening of the immune system, appropriate organ function, and mental development (Nurliyana *et al.*, 2016). Malnutrition contributes to about one-third of mortality (Desmond & Casale, 2017). Mothers play a vital role in selecting and preparing food for better child health. (Ruel *et al.*, 2010). Dull-witted progress of a child's cognitive functioning is seen if the mother's nutrition is

not met during pregnancy and breastfeeding. 59% of women consume an insufficient diverse diet in Bangladesh (Wendt *et al.*, 2019). The urban population faces an economic crisis and more fast-food trends, which affect their health. Policies and programs are essential so mothers can provide optimal child care, especially during pregnancy to the child's 2nd birthday (Haddad *et al.*, 2015). Community-based education on maternal nutrition knowledge was related to a low level of parental education for better child growth (Alderman & Headey, 2017). Objectives of this study was to analyze the association of maternal diet with stunting in the urban population of Faisalabad and to create awareness about the importance of maternal diet to overcome stunting.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

There were two processes on which the survey was designed about the study of Glasow in 2005. At first, a sample strategy was created. The sampling strategy was laid out on how the sample was collected, the selection of a sufficient sample size, and the how the study was carried out. After this, a mechanism for calculating and assessing the dependability of population estimates based on data samples was devised. Calculation of the target number of responses and the intended degree of accuracy for the survey is part of this approach. Pilot testing significantly increased the performance of any survey and was done in two steps. First, the research team thoroughly reviewed the questionnaire. Secondly, before giving it to the entire target population, it was delivered to a small portion of the desired audience (Geldsetzer, 2020). The study collected and analyzed data from 401 mothers chosen at random to study the rate of stunting in the urban population of Faisalabad. A questionnaire was used to collect data. The study took place in almost every area of Faisalabad. The responses to the survey questions confirmed the following requirements.

- a. **Inclusion criteria**
 - Age range: Mothers above 18 years of age

- Mothers having children up to age 36 months
- b. Exclusion criteria**
- Mothers below 18 years of age
 - Mothers having no children or children more than age 36 months

Participants gave their permission to participate in the survey before it began. They were assured that their information would remain confidential and not be shared with anyone. Participants' identities will be kept private, and they can withdraw from the survey at any time before the information is submitted. Data was collected using physical forms to evaluate the association of maternal diet with the rate of stunting of children among the urban population of Faisalabad. The questionnaire is split into five components to get the most information possible. Each component is tailored to our local, socioeconomic, cultural, and available food scenarios. In contrast to open-ended questions, closed-ended questions present a list of options from which to choose. Closed-ended questions are the best for surveys because they provide consistent responses, take less time to complete, and are easier to evaluate (Story & Tait, 2019). Section 1 describes the study's aims and contains essential information on data privacy and participant permission. Mother's and child's data is separated into different sections.

Demographic data section

For each participant, demographic data such as age, gender, city, economic, and health status were gathered (Sidor & Rzymiski, 2020) as it is the analysis of varied traits of the required population, which is vital to sustaining the worth of the study. Section 2 contains demographic data of the child, including age, gender, weight, height, duration of lactation entire lactation period, and age at the start of weaning, whereas section 3 contains the mother's demographic

data, i.e., age, weight, and height. These age groups divide the mother's population into five age groups, i.e., under 18 years, 18-23 years, 24-26 years, 27-29, and 30-35 years. The health status of mothers is also inquired about during pregnancy and current health status.

Anthropometric measurements section

The height of both the child and mother is recorded in the range of about 0.1cm without shoes and with light clothing, per the standard rule (Olfert *et al.*, 2018). The present self and physically measured heights of the participants were reported. The measured height was used in the formula to measure the height for the age Z-score of the child. Weight is another critical physical marker. Both the child's and mother's weight is measured with a weighing machine at roughly 0.5 kg while standing upright in regular clothes. The "current health status" during and after the mothers' pregnancy was also included in this section.

Dietary pattern questionnaire section

A semi-quantitative frequency was employed to examine eating patterns. The categorical variables of daily, weekly, twice a week, once a month, and never were used to measure the frequency of consumption of each meal (Lanham *et al.*, 2019). The dietary questionnaire contained perinatal food frequency questions for commonly consumed foods (One serving).

Statistical analysis

Statistical techniques like chi-square and bivariate correlation analysis have been used to determine the link between a maternal diet and stunting among Faisalabad's urban population (Montgomery, 2017).

The purpose of the questionnaire was to evaluate:

1. Association of maternal diet (food items) with stunting
2. The number of chief meals and snacks eaten per day during pregnancy

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. Mother’s Height at the Time of Pregnancy

Mother’s height (ft inches)	Percent
4.9	2.2
5.0	5.7
5.1	2.7
5.2	5.0
5.3	13.2
5.4	29.7
5.5	17.0
5.6	16.2
5.7	7.2
6.0	1.0
Total	100.0

The percentage of the mother's height at the time of pregnancy are expressed in Table 1. 29.7% were of height of 5.4 ft inches, which is the highest of all, whereas 1% were of height

of 6 ft inches, which is the lowest of all. 2.2% were of height of 4.9, whereas 16.2% were of height of 5.6, 17.0% were of height 5.5, 13.2%, have 5.3 height.

Table 2. Mother’s Age at the Time of Pregnancy

Mother's Age (years)	Percent
18-20	1.0
18-23	11.22
24-26	24.19
27-29	36.66
30-35	26.93
Total	100.0

A mother's age is essential in evaluating a child's stunting. The percentage distribution of the mother's age at the time of pregnancy is in Table.

36.66% were of age group 27-29, the highest of all, whereas 1% were of age group 18-20, 24.19% were of age group 24-26, and 26.93% were of age group 30-35.

Table 3. Mother’s Dietary Pattern During Pregnancy

How many main meals do you eat a day?	Percent
1.0	19.7
2.	38.2
3.0	35.2
4.0	7.0
Total	100.0

The data in Table 3 shows that pregnant mothers followed varying meal patterns during pregnancy. A little over one-third (38.2%) reported eating two meals a day,

while 35.2% consumed three meals daily. Nearly one-fifth (19.7%) limited themselves to just one meal per day, and only a small fraction (7.0%) ate four meals daily. Overall, this indicates that the majority of mothers

(73.4%) had two to three meals a day, while a considerable proportion had fewer than the recommended three meals.

Figure 1. Association between Gender and Height for Age Z-score

The frequency distributions of height for age z-score are shown in Fig 1. 1.2% child population was less than -3 z-score while 5.7% were between -3 and -2 z-score. 49.4% child population were between -2 and 0 z-score whereas 14.2% were between 0 and +2 z-score. 2.2% of the child population were between +2 and +3 z-score and 1.7% of the child population contained -3 z-score. 5.5% of the child population -2 z-score and 16.5% of the child population had a 0 z-score. 2.5% of the

child population had +2 z-score whereas 1% had +3 z-score. Overall, 63% urban population of Faisalabad is stunted. There was a significant association between gender and height for age Z-score. Female children were more stunted than male children, and this significant result follows the findings discussed in both articles (Jiang *et al.*, 2015).

Figure 2. Association of Height for Age Z-score and Lactation Period of Child

The association between “the lactation period of the child in months and height for age-Z-score” is shown in Fig. 5 and results revealed there is a high significance between the lactation period of the child and height for age Z-score. The lactation period is an essential parameter in understanding the quality of growth (Berhanu *et al.*, 2018). The bivariate correlation value of this association is -0.024,

which means there is a negative association between these two variables, i.e., if the lactation period of the child increases, the stunting rate decreases. An increase in the lactation period means breastfeeding should be promoted, and the breastfeeding period needs to be increased to reduce stunting.

Figure 3. Association Between Height of Age Z-score and Binge Eating of Mother

The chi-square test to check the association between “how often you binge-eating due to anxiety, stress, and height for age Z-score” was applied that showed significant results as shown in Fig.6. Most of the respondents fall in the category of sometimes responding to binge eating due to anxiety or stress. Out of 198 children of height for age between -2 and 0, 84 mothers responded sometimes, 66 responded often, and 30 always responded, whereas out of 23 children of height for age Z-score between -3 and -2, 16 mothers responded sometimes, 4 responded never, 2 mothers responded always, and 1 mother responded often. Out of 22 children of height for age Z-score -2, 12 mothers responded sometimes, 5 responded always, 3 responded never, and 2 often

responded, whereas of height for age Z-score -3, out of 7, 1 mother responded sometimes, 2 responded always, 3 responded never, and 1 responded often. The bivariate correlation value of this association is 0.037, which means there is a positive association between these two variables, i.e., the higher the binge eating by mothers during pregnancy, the higher the stunting rate of children will be.

Table 4. Association between Height for Age Z-score and the One Who is Taking Care of the Baby During Your Work Chores

Height for age Z-score	During your work chores, who is taking care of your baby?					Total
	Daycare center	Family	Husband	Maid	Myself	
less than -3	0	5	0	0	0	5
between -3 and -2	0	12	1	6	4	23
between -2 and 0	2	136	12	27	21	198
between 0 and +2	1	28	4	19	5	57
between +2 and +3	0	5	0	2	2	9
-3	0	7	0	0	0	7
-2	0	14	2	2	4	22
0	2	44	6	10	4	66
+2	0	6	1	1	2	10
+3	2	1	0	0	1	4
Total	7	258	26	67	43	401

Chi-squar P value: 0.000**

Bivariate correlation value: -0.03

The chi-square test to check the association between “during your work chores who is taking care of your baby and height for age Z-score” gave a significant association between who is taking care of the baby and daily work chores concerning height for age Z-score. There was no significant association between stunting and exclusive breastfeeding, mothers' frequency of meals taken during pregnancy, mother's weight and age during pregnancy, and family's economic status. These factors are usually considered significant factors in many studies. As it was previously observed that exclusive breastfeeding reduces the rate of stunting to

many folds (Hadi *et al.*, 2021) and it has also been proved that the mother's weight is associated with child stunting (Rahman *et al.*, 2016), the mother's age at the time of pregnancy was also seen as an essential factor in child's stunting (Sartika *et al.*, 2021). Moreover, the mother's demands during pregnancy and the needs of the fetus are also usually ignored in the surroundings which is a key element here. As a result, due to physical or mental stress mother and child both suffer a lot in both manners i.e., physically and mentally.

Table 5. Non-significant food items of groups 1, 2 and 3

Non-significant factors	Chi-square value	P-value	Bivariate correlation value:
Food item rice	44.398	0.159	0.009
Food item pasta	44.848	0.148	0.070
Food item chicken	41.394	0.247	0.020
Food item mutton	45.640	0.130	-0.029
Food item peanut butter	35.144	0.509	-0.006
Food item milk	32.354	0.643	-0.009

Food item yogurt	35.549	0.490	0.044
Food item orange	50.944	0.051	-0.164
Food item orange juice	47.436	0.096	-0.025

Rice is not the staple food of this region, and pasta is not a common food item. The bi-variate correlation values of food items rice, pasta,

chicken, and yogurt are 0.009, 0.070, 0.020, and 0.044, which means that there is a positive relation of stunting with these food items.

Table 6. Non-significant food items of groups 4, 5, 6 and 7

Non-significant factors	Chi-square value	P-value	Bivariate correlation value
Food item spinach	440.123	0.292	-0.005
Food item sweet potato	43.936	0.171	0.094
Food item carrots	41.044	0.259	0.069
Food item melon	39.133	0.331	0.006
Food item apple	34.941	0.519	0.049
Food item banana	43.812	0.174	0.058
Food item grapes	43.694	0.177	0.067
Food item corn	3.565	0.181	0.075
Food item other f & v	39.853	0.303	-0.006
Food items fried food	44.645	0.153	-0.017
Food item butter	41.274	0.251	0.083
Food item margarine	33.580	0.584	-0.022
Food item sour cream	38.009	0.378	-0.024
Food item mayonnaise	46.802	0.107	0.058
Food item salad dressing	45.548	0.132	-0.006
Food item vegetable oil	35.495	0.492	-0.025
Food item chips	36.117	0.463	0.050

In contrast, bi-variate correlation values of food items mutton, peanut butter, milk, orange, and orange juice are -0.029, -0.006, -0.009, -0.164, and -0.025, which means that there is a negative association of stunting with these items consumed, i.e., higher the frequency of these items during pregnancy by mothers, lower the stunting rate. Although there is no significant association between these food items and child stunting, there are various reasons for this awareness of the mother's needs during pregnancy, knowledge, and education related to the demands of the fetus. Dietary habits are not

much developed in this population. That is why no significant association between these items with stunting can be seen. The items having a positive bi-variate correlation value have a positive association with stunting. In contrast, the negative values of the bi-variate correlation mean those food items have a negative association with stunting rate, i.e., the higher the consumption of these food items by mothers during pregnancy, the lower the stunting rate.

Table 7. Non-significant sugary food items of group 7

Non-significant factors	Chi-square value	P-value	Bivariate correlation value
Food item donuts	41.490	0.244	0.047
Food item candy/chocolate	41.724	0.236	0.090
Food item coffee	31.668	0.675	0.029
Food item soda	49.992	0.061	-0.005
Food items, sugary drinks	39.63	0.311	0.035
Food items other sweets	41.195	0.254	-0.015

Most of these are sugary items, and no significant association can be seen between these items with stunting as shown in table 6. Because of gestational diabetes, pregnant ladies try to maintain a balance in their diet and avoid frequent consumption of these items. Moreover, most items like soda and carbonated drinks are considered forbidden during pregnancy. Except for soda and other sweets, the rest of the items have a positive association with stunting, which means the higher the intake of these items, the higher the stunting rate (Athavale *et al.*, 2020).

Conclusion

The results of this study concluded that there is a 37% stunting rate in the urban population which further suggests that this problem needs to be addressed. A balanced maternal diet holds great importance in reducing and preventing this prevalence. In this study, other than maternal diet, some factors have a significant association with stunting; a child's gender, lactation period, and age at the start of weaning are highly significant, with a p-value of 0.000. Out of 48 food items from all seven food groups, only 15 food items have a significant association with stunting. Moreover, the strength of this study is that it is the first study on the evaluation of the association of maternal diet with stunting in the urban population of Faisalabad, and all the respondents were informed about the meaning of the survey and questions to avoid any confusion. The limitation of this study is that we did not use questions about actual dietary habits and behaviors. The study group was specific, so this study's results cannot be generalized. It is recommended that future studies should recruit questionnaires

investigating dietary intakes, such as food frequency questionnaires and 24-hour recall forms. Digital health diet literacy should be emphasized and considered for better health outcomes. Improving digital literacy by focusing on maternal diet during pregnancy is a strategic approach that can influence public behavior and positively reduce stunting.

REFERENCES

Alderman, H. and D.D. Headey. 2017. How important is parental education for child nutrition? World development. 94:448-464.

Athavale, P., N. Khadka, S. Roy, P. Mukherjee, D. Chandra Mohan, B. Turton, and K. S. Gutierrez. 2020. Early childhood junk food consumption, severe dental caries, and undernutrition: A Mixed-Methods Study from Mumbai, India. International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health. 17:8629-8645.

Baig-Ansari, N., M. H. Rahbar, Z. A. Bhutta and S. H. Badruddin. 2006. Child's gender and household food insecurity are associated with stunting among young pakistani children residing in urban squatter settlements. Food and Nutrition Bulletin. 27:114-127.

Benedict, R.K., H.C. Craig, H. Torlesse and R.J. Stoltzfus. 2018. Trends and predictors of optimal breastfeeding among children 0-23 months, South Asia: Analysis of national survey data. Maternal and Child Nutrition. 14:e12698.

- Berhanu, G., S. Mekonnen, M. Sisay. 2018. Prevalence of stunting and associated factors among preschool children: A community based comparative cross sectional study in Ethiopia. *BMC Nutrition*. 4:1-15.
- Suryawan, A., Jalaludin, M.Y., Poh, B.K., Sanusi, R., Tan, V.M.H., Geurts, J.M. and Muhardi, L., 2022. Malnutrition in early life and its neurodevelopmental and cognitive consequences: a scoping review. *Nutrition Research Reviews*, 35(1), pp.136-149.
- Buisman, L. R., Van de Poel, E., O'Donnell, O., & van Doorslaer, E. K. (2019). What explains the fall in child stunting in Sub-Saharan Africa? *SSM-population Health*, 8: 100384-100405.
- Mitra, A., J.T. Bang and F. Abbas. 2021. Do remittances reduce women's acceptance of domestic violence? Evidence from Pakistan. *World Development*. 138:105-149.
- Desmond, C. and D. Casale. (2017). Catch-up growth in stunted children: Definitions and Predictors. *PLoS One*. 12, e0189135-0189152.
- Dhingra, S. and P.L. Pingali. 2021. Effects of short birth spacing on birth-order differences in child stunting: Evidence from India. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*. 118:e2017834118.
- El Taguri, A., I. Betimal, S.M. Mahmud, A.M. Ahmed, O. Goulet, P. Galan and S. Hercberg. 2009. Risk factors for stunting among under-fives in libya. *Public Health Nutrition*. 12:1141-1149.
- Geldsetzer, P. 2020. Use of rapid online surveys to assess people's perceptions during infectious disease outbreaks: A Cross-Sectional Survey on Covid-19. *Journal of Medical Internet Research*. 22:e18790.
- Glasow, P. A. J. R. J. (2005). *Fundamentals of survey Research Methodology*. 18, 2013.
- Haddad, L., E. Achadi, M.A. Bendeck, A. Ahuja, K. Bhatia, Z. Bhutta, M. Blössner, E. Borghi, E. Colecraft and M. De Onis. 2015. The global nutrition report 2014: Actions and accountability to accelerate the world's progress on nutrition. *The Journal of Nutrition*. 145:663-671.
- Hadi, H., F. Fatimatasari, W. Irwanti, C. Kusuma, R.D. Alfiana, M.I.N. Asshiddiqi, S. Nugroho, E.C. Lewis and J. Gittelsohn. 2021. Exclusive breastfeeding protects young children from stunting in a low-income population: A study from eastern Indonesia. *Nutrients*. 13:4264.
- Jawaldeh, A.A., R. Doggui, E. Borghi, H. Aguentaou, L.E. Ammari, A. Abul-Fadl and K. McColl. 2020. Tackling childhood stunting in the eastern mediterranean region in the context of covid-19. *Children*. 7:239-255.
- Jiang, Y., X. Su, C. Wang, L. Zhang, X. Zhang, L. Wang, and Y. Cui. (2015). Prevalence and risk factors for stunting and severe stunting among children under three years old in mid-western rural areas of China. *Child Care Health*. 41:45-51.
- Khalid, H., and E.G. Martin. (2017). Female-headed households associated with lower childhood stunting across culturally diverse regions of Pakistan: Results from a cross-sectional household survey. *Maternal and Child Health Journal*. 21:1967-1984.
- Lanham-New, S. A., Hill, T. R., Gallagher, A. M., & Vorster, H. H. (2019). *Introduction to human nutrition*. John Wiley and Sons 4:112-123.
- McGovern, M. E., A. Krishna, V. M. Aguayo and S. J. Subramanian. (2017). A review of the evidence linking child stunting to economic outcomes. *International Journal of Epidemiology*. 46: 1171-1191.
- Misselhorn, A. and S.L. Hendriks. (2017). A systematic review of sub-national food insecurity research in South Africa: Missed opportunities for policy insights. *PLoS One*, 12:e0182399.

- Montgomery, D. C. (2017). Design and analysis of experiments: John Wiley and Sons.
- Nurliyana, A. R., Z. Mohd Shariff, M. N. Mohd Taib, W.Y. Gan and K. A. Tan. (2016). Early nutrition, growth and cognitive development of infants from birth to 2 years in Malaysia: A study protocol. *BMC Pediatrics*, 16:1-7.
- Nuruddin, R. and W.C. Hadden. (2015). Are pre-school girls more likely to be undernourished in rural Thatta, Pakistan?: A cross-sectional study. *International Journal for Equity in Health*. 14:1-9.
- Olfert, M. D., M. L. Barr, C. M. Charlier, O. A. Famodu, W. Zhou, A. E. Mathews, C. Byrd-Bredbenner and S.E. Colby. (2018). Self-reported vs. measured height, weight, and BMI in young adults. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*. 15:2216-2225.
- Organization, W. H. (2006). WHO child growth standards: length/height-for-age, weight-for-age, weight-for-length, weight-for-height and body mass index-for-age: methods and development: World Health Organization.
- Oruamabo, R. S. (2015). Child malnutrition and the Millennium Development Goals: much haste but less speed? *Archives of Disease in Childhood*. 100:S19-S22.
- Prendergast, A. J. and J. H. Humphrey. (2014). The stunting syndrome in developing countries. *Paediatrics and international child health*, 34:250-265.
- Rahman, M. S., T. Howlader, M. S. Masud and M. L. Rahman. (2016). Association of low-birth weight with malnutrition in children under five years in Bangladesh: do mother's education, socio-economic status, and birth interval matter? *PLoS One*. 11:0157814-0157822.
- Reyes, H., R. Pérez-Cuevas, A. Sandoval, R. Castillo, J. I Santos, S.V. Doubova, G. Gutiérrez. (2004). The family as a determinant of stunting in children living in conditions of extreme poverty: A case-control study. *BMC Public Health*, 4:1-10.
- Ruel, M. T., M. Deitchler and M. Arimond. (2010). Developing simple measures of women's diet quality in developing countries: overview. *The Journal of nutrition*, 140:2048S-2050S.
- Sartika, A. N., M. Khoirunnisa, E. Meiyetriani, E. Ermayani, I. L. Pramesthi and A.J. Nur Ananda. (2021). Prenatal and postnatal determinants of stunting at age 0–11 months: A cross-sectional study in Indonesia. *PLoS One*, 16:0254662-0254662.
- Sidor, A., and P. Rzymiski. (2020). Dietary Choices and Habits during COVID-19 Lockdown: Experience from Poland. *Nutrients*, 12:1657-1667.
- Smith, L. C., and L. Haddad. (2002). How potent is economic growth in reducing undernutrition? What are the pathways of impact? New cross-country evidence. *Economic Development and Cultural Change*. 51:55-76.
- Stevens, G. A., Finucane, M. M., Paciorek, C. J., Flaxman, S. R., White, R. A., Donner, A. J., & Ezzati, M. (2012). Trends in mild, moderate, and severe stunting and underweight, and progress towards MDG 1 in 141 developing countries: a systematic analysis of population representative data. *Lancet*. 380: 824-834.
- Story, D. A. and A.R. Tait. (2019). Survey Research. *Anesthesiology*. 130:192-202.
- Thurow, R. (2016). The first 1,000 days: A crucial time for mothers and children and the world. *Breastfeeding Medicine*. 11:416-418.
- Villar, J., A. T. Papageorghiou, R. Pang, E. O. Ohuma, L. C. Ismail, F. C. Barros, A. Lambert, M. Carvalho, Y. A. Jaffer and E. Bertino. (2014). The likeness of fetal growth and newborn size across non-isolated populations in the INTERGROWTH-21st Project: the Fetal Growth Longitudinal Study and Newborn Cross-Sectional Study. *The Lancet Diabetes and Endocrinology*. 2:781-792.

- Wendt, A. S., T.M. Sparling, J. L. Waid, A. A. Mueller and S. Gabrysch. (2019). Food and Agricultural Approaches to Reducing Malnutrition (FAARM): protocol for a cluster-randomised controlled trial to evaluate the impact of a Homestead Food Production programme on undernutrition in rural Bangladesh. *BMJ Open*. 9:031037-031045.
- WHO, U. (2014). Global Nutrition Targets 2025: Breastfeeding policy brief (WHO/NMH/NHD14. 7). World Health Organization.
- Wieser, S., Brunner, B., Tzogiou, C., Plessow, R., M. B. Zimmermann, J. Farebrother, S. Soofi, Z. Bhatti, I. Ahmed, Z. A. Bhutta and N. Bulletin. (2017). Societal costs of micronutrient deficiencies in 6-59 month-old children in Pakistan. *Food and Nutrition Bulletin*. 38:485-500.

